

EJP SOIL
ARTEMIS

D6.3: Press review

(Final version month 57 of EJP SOIL)

EJP SOIL - ARTEMIS **Deliverable D6.3**

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General Data

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Project title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Project website: www.ejpsoil.eu

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Project duration: 24 months

Topic: CA4/SP3-1

Project type: Medium-sized project

Project coordinator: Klaus Jarosch, Agroscope (AGS), CH

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Abstract

This deliverable summarises the implementation of communication and dissemination activities related to the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project. To effectively disseminate the project results to target groups, the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project used traditional tools, such as scientific and technical papers, press releases, field days, scientific conferences, open days' conferences, Annual Science Days, as well as modern technologies such as webpage and social media channels.

1. Introduction

The EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project was focused on the role of agro-ecological practices in soils' ability to mitigate and abate climate change and it combined an integrated approach based on long-term data, numeric modelling, literature survey and targeted field measurements. Therefore, communication and exploitation activities were important components of the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project to disseminate the results to practitioners and scientists.

The main objectives of the communication and dissemination activities were :

- to build awareness and maximize the impact of the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project among target stakeholders and end-users,
- to exploit an interest of local communities for sustainable climate-smart soil management practices,
- to encourage cooperation of scientists from soil and soil related disciplines,
- to propose relevant findings to policy makers to faster implementation of climate-smart sustainable management practices in Europe.

The EJP SOIL ARTEMIS communication activities targeted to all relevant stakeholders and end-users such as farmers, advisors (including associations), civil society, general public, the scientific community and policy makers.

2. Website

The EJP SOIL ARTEMIS webpage was opened as a subpage of the EJP SOIL portal in March 2023 (M 39). The webpage is available at : <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/eom4soil/into-dialogue/artemis>

The EJP SOIL ARTEMIS sub-webpage includes the following sections:

- **Project objectives** include an overview of the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project aims, keywords and coordinators' contacts;
- **Working plan** contains a short description of each of the 6 Work Packages that compose the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project;
- **Project leaders and partners** includes the list of project partners and webpage link. Clicking on webpage links leads to a general description of each partner and includes a direct access to its webpage;
- **Introductory video**, which provides the main objectives and key takeaways of the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project.

The EJP SOIL ARTEMIS sub-webpage has been maintained during the project implementation.

The EJP SOIL ARTEMIS sub-webpage

3. Introductory video

The introductory video entitled *“Soils provide a multitude of ecosystem services that can contribute both, to the mitigation as well as adaptation to climatic change”* was produced in 2023 and uploaded to the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS sub-webpage in September 2023.

The video gives an introduction to the main projects' aims. For this, coordinator, co-coordinator and leaders of each work package shortly present objectives of each work package. The coordinator Klaus Jarosch (AGS, Switzerland) introduced the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project in the video pill entitled “The EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project”. He stated the main project aim to provide a better understanding on how specific agro-ecological practices affect soil ecosystem service indicators and how these indicators can be assessed in the field. Claudia Di Bene, co-coordinator of Artemis project (CREA, Italy) mentioned which countries and agro-environmental zones were involved into the project in the video pill “Involved partners and long-term field experiments”. Further she specified which approach had been adopted to analyze the effect of agro-ecological practices on soil property mainly carbon dynamics

and nitrogen and also on crop productivity and quality. The leader of WP4 Elena Valkama (LUKE, Finland), introduced the meta-analysis and its application in the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project in the “Meta-analyses” video pill. Ioanna Panagea (EV-ILVO, Belgium), Florian Walder (AGS, Switzerland) and Angeles Prieto Fernandez (INIA-CSIC, Spain) presented development of network of lighthouse farms and interaction of researchers with farmers and stakeholders under the WP 5 in the video pill “Network of different farm across Europe”. Miriam Kizeková (NPPC, Slovakia) presented dissemination activities which run under the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project in video pill “Communication and dissemination”.

Moreover, participants from each project’ country presented their activities in frame of the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS. Marco Acutis (University of Milan, Italy) spoke about the use of simulation model (e.g. Armosa model) in agriculture and possibilities to evaluate how different agricultural practices affect the soil health and mitigate climate change in the video pill “*Simulation models for improving yields*”. Julia Fohrafellner (BIOS Science, Austria) as a deputy leader WP 4 presented the establishment of actual statistical criteria which are supposed to help soil agricultural scientists and also policymakers to read through meta-analysis correctly in the video pill entitled “*Quality assessment in meta-analyses*”.

In addition, the video pills *The EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project, Meta-analyses and Quality assessment in meta-analyses* were posted on Twitter (X net).

4. Press releases

The official press releases of the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS help to raise the interest and awareness of the project and will be transferred to press offices at national and European level and EJP SOIL WP9.

Two articles were published in the EJP SOIL newsletter during the life span of the project:

1. The 1st article with a title “*Project Artemis aims to deliver new knowledge on the resilience of agroecological systems to withstand climate extremes*” (available at: <https://ejpsoil.eu/about-ejp-soil/news-events-newsletters/item/artikel/project-artemis-aims-to-deliver-new-knowledge-on-the-resilience-of-agroecological-systems-to-withstand-climate-extremes>) was published in the EJP SOIL Newsletter, in December 2023. The objective of the article was to provide the most important information on the scope and the main outputs of the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project.
2. The 2nd article entitled “*Methods and analysis tools for assessing the sustainability of cropping systems and ecosystem services of agricultural soils*” was published in the EJP SOIL Newsletter, in February 2024 (available at: <https://ejpsoil.eu/about-ejp-soil/news-events-newsletters/item/artikel/methods-and-analysis-tools-for-assessing-the-sustainability-of-cropping-systems-and-ecosystem-services-of-agricultural-soils>). This article was devoted the workshop on data analytics methods and tools to assess cropping system sustainability and soil ecosystem services which was held in Rome in September 2023.

EJP SOIL Newsletter, 01/2024

Further, a published manuscript on the use of “effective microorganisms” was also translated into English, German and French in a laymen version article to improve dissemination with practitioners:

[Can Effective Microorganisms Influence Green-Manure Decomposition? - Agrarforschung Schweiz](#)

5. Social media

An **X (Twitter)** account (@EJPSOIL_Artemis) was opened in November 2022. Here, project partners posted latest project events and actively follow soil-agriculture-related official organisations and platforms such as EJP SOIL, FAO, Agorecology Europe, IFOAM Organics Europe, EIP AGRI, Horizon Europe in order to enrich the Twitter ARTEMIS account content and attract more followers.

The content was regularly updated and included news and events organized with ARTEMIS members' participation. Totally, the ARTEMIS partners made 69 posts which included events such as EJPSOIL Annual Science Days in Riga and Vilnius, Days of Soil, Biodiversity, Earth; national EJP SOIL workshops, scientific conferences, field days and excursions for farmers and agricultural practitioners were regularly posted.

To the end of September 2024, the X EJP SOIL ARTEMIS (Twitter) account had 158 followers. In total, 69 posts were made on the X account for dissemination purposes.

X (Twitter) account EJP SOIL ARTEMIS

6. Workshop on data analytics methods and tools to assess cropping system sustainability and soil ecosystem services

In September 2023, the workshop *Methods and analytical tools for assessing the sustainability of farming systems and soil ecosystem services* was held in Rome. The workshop was organized by the project partners CREA and LUKE and was promoted by the project coordinator Dr. Klaus Jarosch (Agroscope, Switzerland) and the co-coordinator Dr. Claudia Di Bene (CREA-AA, Italy).

The workshop was into three modules:

- Research synthesis and meta-analysis in agro-environmental science,
- Trade-off analysis', the trade-off assessment system,
- The ARMOSA model - Theory and first application.

The workshop was attended by 25 researchers from 7 European countries, including around 15 young researchers.

7. Scientific events and publications

Scientific results have been published presented at national and international conferences such as EJP SOIL Annual Science Days in Riga and Vilnius, Northern Europe “4 per 1000” Regional Meeting, Congreso Internacional de Agroecología.

From March 2024, Zenodo repository account (https://zenodo.org/communities/artemis_2024) was opened to deposit the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS outputs.